

NITRO D-CELL PROJECT

Authors:

Víctor Dato (GFM Fotovoltaica); Sergio Luján (GFM Fotovoltaica); Jesús Martín-Borja (GFM Fotovoltaica); Francisco Fueyo-González (HFC); María Cuartero-González (Instituto IMDEA Energía); Javier R. Guerrero (Instituto IMDEA Energía), Julio Lado (Instituto IMDEA Energía); Enrique García-Quismondo (Instituto IMDEA Energía); Jesús Palma (Instituto IMDEA Energía)

Abstract

A New Pathway for Producing Green Hydrogen with Lower Energy Consumption and Nitrogen Compound Valorisation

The consortium formed by GFM, HFC and IMDEA Energy has successfully completed the first three phases of the Nitro D-Cell project, demonstrating that the incorporation of nitrogen-based derivatives into the electrolyte of electrochemical cells enables increased hydrogen production while significantly reducing energy consumption compared with conventional alkaline water electrolysis. These results open a promising pathway towards more efficient electrolyser systems for green hydrogen production.

Background and Motivation

Green hydrogen production through alkaline electrolysis faces a fundamental challenge: its high energy consumption, which limits its competitiveness compared with fossil-based hydrogen.

In this context, the Nitro D-Cell project was conceived as an initiative aimed at developing a new generation of electrolyser systems capable of producing hydrogen while simultaneously valorising nitrogen-containing compounds present in industrial liquid streams. The technological approach is based on partially replacing the conventional water oxidation reaction with the electrooxidation of nitrogen derivatives. This strategy significantly reduces the energy requirements of the process while simultaneously increasing hydrogen production.

PROJECT	Nitro D-Cell
TECHNOLOGY	Alkaline electrolysis using nitrogen-rich electrolytes
STRUCTURE	Four work packages (WP1–WP4)
OBJECTIVE	Increased hydrogen production and lower energy consumption compared with conventional alkaline electrolysis

WP1 | Active Anode Materials: Electrooxidation of Nitrogen Derivatives

The first work package focused on identifying and characterising the most suitable active materials for the oxidation reaction occurring at the positive electrode of the cell. The anode represents the key component of the Nitro D-Cell concept, as it is the electrode where the electrooxidation of nitrogen derivatives present in the electrolyte takes place. This reaction replaces the conventional oxygen evolution reaction and enables operation at significantly lower potentials.

The methodology consisted of preparing different nickel-based active materials in the form of electrochemical inks deposited onto glassy carbon electrodes. Electrochemical performance was evaluated using a three-electrode cell configuration, as shown in Figure 1. This approach enabled the response of each formulation towards the nitrogen derivatives present in the electrolyte to be isolated and accurately quantified.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the three-electrode cell used during the experiments performed in Work Package 1.

Following a comparative analysis of catalytic activity, stability and selectivity, the most promising materials were selected for integration into subsequent project stages.

Among the materials evaluated, **NiOOH (nickel oxyhydroxide)** emerged as one of the most active catalysts for the oxidation of nitrogen derivatives, combining good electronic conductivity with excellent stability under alkaline conditions.

KEY RESULT

Selected anode material: NiOOH deposited on glassy carbon.

Figure 2. Deposition of active material ink onto the active surface of a glassy carbon electrode.

WP2 | Cathode Materials for Hydrogen Production

The second work package focused on the development of the cathodic electrode, responsible for the water reduction reaction and therefore for hydrogen generation. The key requirements for cathode materials include high corrosion resistance, good electrical conductivity, large active surface area and structural integrity. The challenge was to identify materials capable of maintaining high activity towards the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER) under the strongly alkaline conditions characteristic of the nitrogen-rich electrolyte employed in the project.

Various alloys with proven resistance to severe alkaline environments were evaluated through three-electrode cell testing, including stainless steel, nickel and Elinvar (a low thermal expansion iron-nickel alloy). Subsequently, the effect of surface coatings based on nanoporous metal oxides was investigated with the objective of improving corrosion resistance while simultaneously modifying electrochemical performance.

The porous architecture provided by these coatings offers a high-specific-area protective surface and creates preferential nucleation sites for gas bubble formation and detachment, thereby enhancing electrode operation during electrochemical reactions.

Comparative testing revealed significant differences among the evaluated systems in terms of exchange current density and HER overpotential.

Among all the materials tested, coated stainless steel exhibited the best balance between catalytic activity, chemical stability and scalability, establishing itself as the reference cathode material for the project.

KEY RESULT

Selected cathode material: coated stainless steel.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the coatings evaluated in Work Package 2 to improve hydrogen production performance at the cathode.

WP3 | Development and Validation of the Cell Prototype

With the anode and cathode materials defined during the previous phases, the third work package focused on integrating these materials into a functional cell prototype. This stage represented the transition from three-electrode laboratory testing—ideal for fundamental electrochemical studies—to a complete electrochemical device in which both electrodes interact under conditions closer to those encountered in real applications.

One of the most relevant challenges during this stage was the selection of the structural support material onto which the active material inks would be deposited. Three support structures commonly used in electrolysis systems were evaluated: graphite felt, carbon paper and nickel foam. Active nickel-based materials previously identified in WP1 were deposited onto each support and subsequently characterised under operational conditions.

The results established a clear hierarchy regarding both support selection and the optimal electrode combination.

Graphite felt demonstrated the best overall performance in terms of conductivity, porosity and compatibility with the electrochemical inks developed during WP1. The combination of a graphite felt anode impregnated with NiOOH ink and a coated stainless-steel cathode delivered the highest hydrogen production rates while simultaneously achieving the lowest energy consumption among all configurations evaluated.

KEY RESULT

Optimal cell configuration: graphite felt anode + NiOOH ink / coated stainless-steel cathode with nanoporous material.

Figure 4. Nitro D-Cell electrolysis prototype used for the experiments conducted in Work Package 3.

WP4 | Scale-Up: Construction of a Five-Cell Stack (Ongoing)

The fourth and final work package aims to demonstrate the viability of the Nitro D-Cell concept at a larger scale by moving beyond a single-cell configuration towards a multi-cell electrolyser stack. This phase represents the most challenging engineering stage of the project, as electrochemical scale-up introduces several issues that do not appear at laboratory scale, including fluid management, homogeneous current distribution, assembly sealing, material uniformity and coating reproducibility.

Before integrating the electrodes developed in WP3 into the final stack under construction, an intermediate scale-up phase is being conducted to analyse the effects associated with increased system size. For this purpose, the experimental setup shown in Figure 6 is being used.

The team is currently constructing a five-cell stack intended for testing under controlled operating conditions. Validation of the stack will allow confirmation of the results obtained during the previous phases, identification of scale-related effects and establishment of the foundations required for the design of larger-capacity systems in the future.

CURRENT STATUS

Five-cell stack currently under construction and scheduled for validation under controlled conditions.

Figure 5. Schematic representation of the five-cell stack under development in Work Package 4.

Figure 6. Nitro D-Cell electrolysis prototype used during the scale-up studies of Work Package 4.

Conclusions and Future Outlook

Throughout its first three phases, the Nitro D-Cell project has demonstrated the consistency and robustness of the electrochemical concept on which it is based. The incorporation of nitrogen derivatives as a functional component of the electrolyte has enabled a reconfiguration of the anode reaction, reducing the required cell potential and consequently lowering the energy cost associated with hydrogen production.

The materials identified during the project—NiOOH and nickel ferrocyanide at the anode, together with coated stainless steel at the cathode, both integrated on graphite-felt-based architectures—offer a suitable combination of catalytic activity, chemical stability and manufacturability for integration into larger-scale prototypes.

The completion of WP4 and the validation of the five-cell stack will be decisive for assessing the technology transfer potential of the developed solution. Should stack-level testing confirm the performance observed at individual cell level, the Nitro D-Cell concept could become a valuable contribution to the green hydrogen technology ecosystem, particularly in contexts where nitrogen-rich streams such as industrial effluents or wastewater can be integrated directly into the process logic as functional electrolyte components.

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